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Standardization Roadmap-v1

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Abstract:	This deliverable presents all the relevant activities performed in the context of standardization and standards observation during the first 18 months of the MEDINA project.
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Table of Contents

Terms and abbreviations.....	6
Executive Summary	7
1 Introduction	8
1.1 About this deliverable	8
1.2 Document structure	8
2 The Approach to Standardization in MEDINA.....	9
2.1 Standardization Approach.....	9
2.2 Scouting - Identifying standardization activities relevant to MEDINA.....	10
2.3 Influencing - MEDINA contributing to the development of Standards / Good Practices	10
2.4 Transferring – Leveraging standard for scientific and technical activities in MEDINA ..	11
3 Report on MEDINA’s Standardization / Best-Practices Activities	12
3.1 EU Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services (ENISA EUCS).....	12
3.1.1 Overview of ENISA AHWG	12
3.1.2 Contribution to Thematic Groups (TG)	12
3.1.3 Contribution to ENISA EUCS Experimentation	15
3.2 CEN CENELEC’s Technical Specification for EUCS.....	17
3.3 Code of practice for information security controls based on ISO/IEC 27002 for cloud services (ISO/IEC 27017).....	17
3.4 Open Security Controls Assessment Language (NIST OSCAL)	18
3.5 The Gaia-X Initiative	19
3.6 Security Metrics and Cloud Controls Matrix (Cloud Security Alliance)	20
4 Standardization Roadmap (First Iteration)	21
4.1 Methodological Approach.....	21
4.2 Topics for Standardization.....	21
4.3 Next Steps.....	25
5 Conclusions	27
6 References	28
APPENDIX A: Assurance Levels in EUCS (Draft November 2020).....	29
APPENDIX B: Basic EUCS Questionnaire Contribution (excerpt).....	34
APPENDIX C: Report to ENISA on EUCS Experimentation	36

List of Tables

TABLE 1. MEDINA APPROACH TO ENISA EXPERIMENTATION.....	16
TABLE 2. CONTRIBUTION TO NIST OSCAL RELATED TO EUCS	18
TABLE 3. TOPICS FOR STANDARDIZATION ROADMAP.....	22
TABLE 4. MEDINA ROADMAP - NEXT STEPS.....	25

List of Figures

FIGURE 1. MEDINA'S APPROACH TO STANDARDIZATION.....	9
FIGURE 2. CONTRIBUTED ENISA EUCS' THEMATIC GROUPS	13
FIGURE 3. PROCESSES RELATED TO THE ISSUANCE AND MANAGEMENT OF EUCS CERTIFICATES.	14

Terms and abbreviations

AHWG	AdHoc Working Group
AISBL	Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif
BSI	Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik
CAB	Conformance Assessment Body
CCM	Cloud Controls Matrix
CEN CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CSA or EU CSA	EU Cybersecurity Act
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
DIN	Deutsches Institut für Normung
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EUCS	EU Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services
ENISA	EU Agency for Cybersecurity
ESG	Expert Stakeholder Group
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
ISO/IEC	International Standards Organization / International Electrotechnical Commission
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ISACA	Information Systems Audit and Control Association
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
SDO	Standards Development Organization
SSO	Standards Setting Organization
SW	Software
TG	Thematic Groups
TOM	Technical and Organizational Measure
TS	Technical Specification
OSCAL	Open Security Controls Assessment Language
POC	Proof Of Concept
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents MEDINA’s standardization activities and associated main results, which took place during the reporting period (M1-M18). Documented activities include the methodological approach that has been developed by the consortium to guarantee the creation of efficient synergies with standardization bodies and good practices working groups. Furthermore, this deliverable also presents the results of MEDINA’s activities related to standardization, including the adoption and influence of relevant works in the cloud cybersecurity certification field. Finally, we also report on the initial standardization roadmap which is being created by MEDINA to support sustainability of the produced project outcomes, and uptake of the EU Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services (EUCS).

1 Introduction

This section provides an overview of the content documented in this deliverable.

1.1 About this deliverable

The topic of standardization plays an important role in MEDINA, just as reflected by Task 7.4 which additionally contributes to the project's sustainability actions coordinated by WP7. On one hand, our project constantly surveys the standardization landscape (including industrial good practices) to facilitate early adopters, the integration of contributed frameworks into their own ecosystems. On the other hand, MEDINA is actively contributing to a selected group of standards as a mean to support the project's sustainability even after its lifetime. In this context, it is important to clarify our notion of "standardization", as referred not only to the activities of established Standards Developing Organizations (SDOs like ISO/IEC and ETSI), but also to those taking place within Standards Setting Organizations (SSOs e.g., Cloud Security Alliance). In both cases fruitful/efficient synergies can only be built if the project develops the right approach for interacting with relevant SDOs and SSOs.

This deliverable covers the reporting period (M1-M18) and presents the methodological approach developed by MEDINA to internally leverage and influence relevant standards, and also industrial good practices. Furthermore, initial activities and results of applying the developed approach are also discussed. Finally, an initial version of MEDINA's proposed standardization roadmap is also discussed. Our roadmap aims to support sustainability of technical contributions from MEDINA, while at the same time supporting the EUCS uptake thanks to the activities in Task 7.4.

1.2 Document structure

The rest of this document is organized in the following manner:

- Section 2 reports on the methodological approach developed by MEDINA to adopt/influence both SDOs and SSOs.
- Section 3 presents the current activities of MEDINA withing selected standards and good practices.
- Section 4 discusses the initial version of MEDINA's standardization roadmap.
- Finally, Section 5 presents our conclusions and future work.

2 The Approach to Standardization in MEDINA

Despite the evident benefits brought to research projects thanks to the adoption and influence on standards (including industrial good practices), previous experience has shown that unstructured approaches have a negative effect on both usage of resources and general uptake of generated outcomes. When technical work packages are not aware of relevant standards in their field, there is a high risk of lacking interoperability and therefore damaging their planned exploitation activities. Furthermore, if a project fails to timely identify and create synergies with relevant standardization activities, it is very unlikely that scientific and technical outcomes will influence the corresponding SDO or SSO.

Which are the elements to develop an efficient approach to standardization? When it is the right point in time for projects to start working on standardization activities? Despite there is no easy answer to these questions, this section will discuss the approach developed by MEDINA to maximize the benefits of standardization, in particular related to the topic of continuous certification.

2.1 Standardization Approach

MEDINA's standardization approach consists of three interrelated processes, namely:

1. **Scouting**, where project experts constantly survey the SDO/SSO landscape to identify relevant activities for MEDINA.
2. **Transfer**, where identified standards/good practices are analysed and leveraged into MEDINA's technical activities.
3. **Influencing**, where MEDINA actively engages in the development of identified standards/good practices.

These processes can be seen in Figure 1 and are further explained in the rest of this section.

Figure 1. MEDINA's Approach to Standardization

2.2 Scouting - Identifying standardization activities relevant to MEDINA

A central role in our standardization approach relates to the continuous survey of the relevant SDO/SSO landscape i.e., the so-called “scouting” phase. During this stage all technical WPs participate, under the coordination of WP7, to bring their expertise related either to (i) the need for alignment with existing standards, or (ii) potential contributions to specific SDO/SSO initiatives.

The team in WP7 supports in coordination activities related to standardization in MEDINA, specifically for retrieving/summarizing identified standards from those SDO/SSO where a liaison exists (e.g., ENISA EUCS), evaluating the MEDINA-relevance of new works being discussed in standardization bodies (e.g., the revision to ISO/IEC 27017 presented in Section 3.3), and orchestrating the project’s contributions to selected SDO/SSO initiatives.

Scouting is an essential activity in WP7-standardization because it makes more efficient the use of available MEDINA resources. Please take into account that “continuous cloud cybersecurity certification” is a novel topic in relevant SDO/SSO, and it is resulting in multiple workstreams (see as an example the thematic groups from ENISA EUCS in Section 3.1.2) which need to be prioritized in order to avoid scattering efforts.

Once the “scouting” has identified relevant SDO/SSO activities, with the support of MEDINA’s WPs experts, then it must be collaboratively decided if the project should contribute (influence) or transfer standardization know-how to its technical activities. Both processes are presented in Section 2.3 and Section 2.4 respectively.

Finally, it is worth to notice that MEDINA’s scouting activities play a relevant role in the creation of the project’s standardization roadmap, which is presented in Section 4.

2.3 Influencing - MEDINA contributing to the development of Standards / Good Practices

Part of the project’s sustainability depends on creating a “technical legacy” of its WP2-WP6 activities. From a WP7-standardization perspective, such legacy corresponds to what MEDINA can contribute to well-scoped SDO/SSO activities which have been identified during the scouting phase (see Section 2.2). It is well-known that standardization activities can have a very long timeline (sometimes lasting 20+ months until the final standard is released), therefore the importance of focusing only on those activities where MEDINA’s impact can be maximized. Furthermore, if a standardization activity can expand beyond the project’s lifetime then there must be a clear commitment from participating partners to continue their collaboration with their own resources at a given time. In some cases, this decision is directly related to the partners’ exploitation plans, which are further discussed in D7.6 [1] and D7.7 [2].

In any case, and once WP7 identifies one or more relevant SDO/SSO initiatives, then it is time to orchestrate the actual technical contributions. From a high-level perspective, the “influencing” process consists of the following steps:

1. **Liaising with the corresponding SDO/SSO:** this is an essential step in order to guarantee that the project’s contributions will be formally taken into account with the corresponding standardization body. In particular SSOs (e.g., Cloud Security Alliance) have an open (and cost-free) process for contributing to their initiatives, which facilitates for projects like MEDINA to provide contributions from different technical partners. The situation is different for many SDOs, where in order to contribute (and not only to participate as an Observer) it is necessary to become a (paid) member e.g.,

ISO/IEC and the German DIN. During the reporting period, MEDINA partners (Bosch, TECNALIA, and FhG) created liaisons with ENISA (AdHoc WG on EUCS), Gaia-X, CEN CENELEC (CEN/CLC/JTC 13/WG 2), ISO/IEC (JTC1 SC27/WG1), German DIN (NA 043-01-27-01 AK), Cloud Security Alliance (Cloud Security Metrics WG), and NIST (OSCAL WG).

2. **Participating in related SDO/SSO activities:** once the liaison has been created by MEDINA, then it is time to start the actual work of participating in the corresponding SDO/SSO meetings in order to identify the topics/projects to contribute, and guarantee that established deadlines will be fulfilled.
3. **Orchestration of MEDINA contributions:** this is an interactive step, where WP7 coordinates with the technical WP2-WP6 to manage contributions on identified SDO/SSO activities. Depending on the organization, there might be substantial differences related to the way of writing and submitting feedback from MEDINA, but in any case, the WP7-standardization lead must carefully consider and follow the related guidelines.
4. **Positioning MEDINA contributions:** submitting a contribution to the SDO/SSO does not mean that it will simply make it into the final published standard. The contribution must be well positioned using objective/sound arguments, to increase its chances of publication at the identified SDO/SSO. This is an interactive process where WP7 might need to come back to step (3) in order to refine the contribution as needed.

The described process has been leveraged by MEDINA, and ongoing contributions are presented in Section 3.

2.4 Transferring – Leveraging standard for scientific and technical activities in MEDINA

Complementary to MEDINA’s process for influencing SDO/SSO, we can also find the WP7-standardization activity related to “bringing” standards to the technical activities from WP2-WP6. In a nutshell, it refers to transferring standards (e.g., machine-readable formats, good certification practices, assessment methodologies) so they can be leveraged or modelled by the technical MEDINA activities. This activity supports early adoption/interoperability of produced outcomes thanks to their alignment to existing standards, and also guarantees that MEDINA’s framework follows the standard in the way it was meant to be.

During the reporting period we realized that this “transferring” activity was essential for the EUCS requirements and processes being implemented by the MEDINA framework, where the work created by ENISA was being directly leveraged by the technical WP2-WP6 activities. Thanks to this activity, the produced MEDINA framework is expected to have a major impact in future (commercial) products seeking also to implement EUCS. Relevant “transferring” activities are reported in the next section.

3 Report on MEDINA’s Standardization / Best-Practices Activities

This section reports the consortium’s activities with relevant SDO/SSO initiatives, which were selected based on the *Scouting* process described in the Section 2 and comprised both *Influencing* and *Transferring* tasks.

3.1 EU Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services (ENISA EUCS)

Probably the most relevant standardization activity from the MEDINA perspective is the one being led by ENISA on the topic of EUCS. MEDINA has both *Influenced* and *Transferred* know-how to ENISA EUCS, just as presented below.

3.1.1 Overview of ENISA AHWG

On March 2020, ENISA launched a so-called ad-hoc working group (AHWG) to support the European Commission (EC) in preparing the draft candidate cybersecurity certification scheme for cloud services¹.

Twenty (20) members were selected “*according to the highest standards of expertise, aiming to ensure appropriate balance according to the specific issues in question, between the public administrations of the Member States, the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies, and the private sector, including industry, users, and academic experts in network and information security*”².

According to the terms of reference in the call for candidates, the group of experts was expected to provide ENISA with input on the scope, purpose, requirements, assurance level definitions, conformity assessment methodologies and monitoring of the compliance, statement of conformity, and certification lifecycle related to the novel EUCS.

Out of the twenty selected members, two of them are part of the MEDINA project, namely Bosch (Dr. Jesus Luna Garcia) and TECNALIA (Dra. Leire Orue-Echevarria Arrieta).

The work in the AHWG of ENISA has been distributed in Thematic Groups (TG), which are dedicated sub-groups to work extensively and exclusively in one specific EUCS topic. Each TG was supported by a rapporteur (selected from the 20 experts), and at the time of writing are still meeting in a weekly manner since November 2020. Our project’s engagement activities with those TG are reported next.

3.1.2 Contribution to Thematic Groups (TG)

ENISA defined *nine* TGs, out of which MEDINA actively contributed to *five* during the period covered by this deliverable. Those five specific TGs were selected based on the approach described in Section 2, and their relationship with our technical activities can be seen in Figure 2.

From a MEDINA’s perspective, each contributed TG was classified either as *Foundational* or *Follow-up*. The former means that the TG outcome was part of the original EUCS draft from December 2020, whereas the latter refers to follow-up EUCS activities of the ENISA AHWG.

¹ https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/standards/adhoc_wg_calls/ahWG02

²

https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/standards/adhoc_wg_calls/ahWG02/tor_ahwg02_cloud/@@download/file/ToR%20ahWG-Cloud%20Services.pdf

Notwithstanding its Foundational or Follow-up nature, the consortium actively engaged with the illustrated TGs just as explained in the rest of this section.

TG1 – Assurance Levels

- WP2 – WP4
- Keywords: foundational, risk management, certification processes

TG2 – Security Controls

- WP2
- Keywords: foundational, security controls frameworks, metrics, catalogue

TG3 – Assessment Methods

- WP3 – WP4
- Keywords: foundational, certification processes, certificate lifecycle, evidence

TG8 – Guidance on Controls

- WP2
- Keywords: follow-up, good practices, continuous monitoring, experimentation

TG9 CS Basic Questionnaire

- WP2, WP4
- Keywords: follow-up, risk management, preparedness

Figure 2. Contributed ENISA EUCS' Thematic Groups

3.1.2.1 TG1 – Assurance Levels

The aim of this group was to determine the different scope and dimensions needed to define the different assurance levels that the EU CSA requires. The two AHWG members of MEDINA participated in this group's discussions.

The EU CSA only states that there should be three levels of assurance (i.e. basic, substantial and high), but does not provide further details. It is up to the certification scheme under scope to determine how these levels will be characterized. In the case of the EUCS, the approach of “incremental dimensions” was selected. That is, assurance levels have dimensions where the security requisites are gradually incremented. MEDINA partners participated in the discussions, provided comments and alternative texts to the assurance level definitions, **in particular related to the notion of continuous (automated) monitoring for High Assurance**. That work was then leveraged into the activities of WP2-WP4 for topics like risk management (WP2), continuous collection of evidence (WP3), and conceptualization of operational effectiveness (WP4).

TG1 finished its activities in December 2021. For more information on EUCS-defined assurance levels (outcome of TG1) please refer to Appendix A.

3.1.2.2 TG2 – Security Controls

TG2 is the foundational group devoted to the definition of the categories, security controls, security requirements and their placement in one or another level of assurance. This activity is also fundamental for MEDINA, because it provides the actual set of technical and organizational measures (TOMs) for certifying a cloud service.

Taking as baseline existing schemes and control catalogues, the group met weekly to discuss the structure of the requirements, the requirements themselves, their scope, the wording and the assurance level. The MEDINA coordinator was also the rapporteur and led the discussions, in collaboration with the ENISA chair. In the context of TG2, MEDINA provided ENISA with the mapping of EUCS with other schemes, just as reported in D2.1 [3].

TG2 finished its activities in December 2021, although follow-up activities are taking place in the context of CEN CENELEC (cf. Section 3.2). The set of requirements elicited by TG2 are part of MEDINA's *Catalogue of Controls and Security Schemes* (please refer to D2.1).

3.1.2.3 TG3 – Assessment Methods

This foundational thematic group was devoted to the definition of the conformity assessment method(s) that will be used by EUCS. For the level of assurance basic, it was determined that an evidence-based self-assessment with a third party involved would be the appropriate one, while for the substantial and high levels of assurance a meta-methodology based on ISAE 3402³ and ISO 17065⁴ has been designed.

MEDINA participated in the weekly TG3 discussions, reviewing the generated methodological document thanks to the feedback being provided by our CAB partner NIXU. One of the main outcomes from TG3, which currently drives the MEDINA activities related to the certification lifecycle, are the management processes summarized in Figure 3. TG3 finished its activities in December 2021.

Figure 3. Processes related to the issuance and management of EUCS certificates⁵

³ ISAE 3402 “Assurance Reports on Controls at a Service Organization”

⁴ ISO 17065 “Conformity assessment — Requirements for bodies certifying products, processes and services”

⁵ Based on ENISA EUCS draft from December 2020

3.1.2.4 TG8 – Guidance on Controls

After December 2021, ENISA organized a set of follow-up EUCS activities targeting both the standardization and uptake of the developed scheme. Guidance and good practices related to implementing and auditing the scheme are needed not only by EUCS, but also for supporting the adoption of the MEDINA framework. One of such follow-up activities related to TG9, which was born during the so-called experimentation stage (cf. Section 3.1.3) where it became clear from the comments of the participants, that guidance is needed to ensure the success of EUCS.

The MEDINA coordinator participated in the discussions of the TG8 approach, the depth level and the structure of the guidance to be developed. Furthermore, MEDINA has provided the reference implementations described in D3.1 [4] as potential input for the guidance of the controls of assurance level high (continuous monitoring). This is an ongoing activity, which is expected to finalize by the end of 2022.

3.1.2.5 TG9 – Questionnaire for Basic Assurance

Another EUCS *follow-up* activity which is tightly related to the technical tasks in MEDINA relates to the so-called self-assessment questionnaire (i.e., EUCS basic assurance). The goal of ENISA is to develop a methodology and questionnaire for guiding CSPs and CABs in aspects related to the achievement of a basic assurance EUCS certificate.

The work that partner TECNALIA is doing in WP3 with the questionnaires to assess the basic level of assurance (cf. D3.1 [4]) has been shared and discussed with ENISA. At the time of writing this deliverable, the MEDINA approach and questionnaires were being leveraged by the TG9 participants. The questionnaires that TECNALIA provided had approximately 500 questions as they were mostly a decomposition of the requirements, but included also the definition and identification of evidences (i.e., documents, logs or any kind of information that can potentially support a statement), which up until now had not been previously considered in-depth in past discussions. An excerpt of the developed MEDINA questionnaire, which was provided to TG9 can be seen in Appendix B.

The challenges and main effort expected to comply with the approach for the assessment of basic assurance level does not strive in the number of questions that CSPs need to complete, but in finding the right evidence that proves that that requirement is fully complied with. This lesson learned from MEDINA has been now also included in the questionnaires.

It is also worth to notice that the developed TG9 questionnaires are also being analysed for MEDINA's SATRA tool (cf., D2.6 [5] on static risk assessment), and similarly for the activities related to the assessment of organizational evidences (cf., D3.4 [6] on organizational measures). TG9 is an ongoing activity, which is expected to finalize by the end of 2022.

3.1.3 Contribution to ENISA EUCS Experimentation

During March 2021, a call for “EUCS experimentation” was released by ENISA with the goal of verifying the auditability and efficiency of the candidate draft scheme, where stakeholders were able to lead evaluation on specific parts of EUCS. The call was only open to members of the AHWG, and therefore to participate the team was supposed to apply only through a member of the AHWG. Furthermore, the team must be comprised of at least a CSP and a CAB. This “experimentation” allowed ENISA to get feedback on the draft candidate scheme and build guidance, and also allowed stakeholders taking a first step ahead on the future cloud certification scheme and gain maturity. A condition for the experimentation was to consider a real use case, based on an actual cloud service, and to include a return-on-experience phase to the ad hoc Working Group.

MEDINA considered this call for EUCS experimentation as a great opportunity to disseminate the project’s activities, while at the same time contributing to the uptake of EUCS and the framework under development. In that context, MEDINA proposal targeted the experimentation of automated monitoring requirements extracted from the EUCS High Assurance. Participants on this ENISA POC were two cloud service providers (Fabasoft and Bosch), and one CAB (NIXU). As mentioned earlier in this chapter, Bosch is part of the ENISA AHWG.

Table 1 shows the original approach as proposed to ENISA for the POC.

Table 1. MEDINA approach to ENISA Experimentation

Stage	Explanation	Comment
1	Selection of EUCS requirements	The requirements will be extracted from EUCS High Assurance (Annex A), where the keyword “automated monitoring” has been used. Our aim is to evaluate for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bosch: 5 different EUCS requirements, from at least 3 different Azure services. • Fabasoft: 5 different EUCS requirements for the Fabasoft Cloud.
2	Selection of automated monitoring policies (Bosch only)	The automated monitoring policies (for the Azure platform) will be selected as they correspond to a set of chosen EUCS requirements. Such policies will come from the custom catalogue of Azure.
3	Experiment the EUCS concept of <i>operational effectiveness</i> for automated monitoring requirements	Bosch: will deploy its selected policies in the Microsoft Azure platform for a period 90 days corresponding to the EUCS notion of <i>operational effectiveness</i> . In the scope of this experiment will be a specific Bosch PaaS solution deployed in Microsoft Azure. Fabasoft: will apply the selected requirements to current implementations that are monitored with app.telemetry ⁶ for other standards, like BSI C5: 2020, for a period of time corresponding to the EUCS notion of <i>operational effectiveness</i> .
4	Document results, observations and challenges	A report will be produced to compile the lessons learned, results, and foreseen challenges related to the real-world usage of the experimented EUCS requirements. The report will be also contributed by NIXU, in order to provide the perspectives of both CSP and CAB.

The final report delivered to ENISA by the MEDINA team can be found in Appendix C. This experience was also integrated into the technical activities for developing the MEDINA framework, in particular related to the evidence collectors and the definition of operational effectiveness which is in the scope of WP4.

⁶ <https://www.fabasoft.com/en/products/fabasoft-apptelemetry>

3.2 CEN CENELEC's Technical Specification for EUCS

As part of ENISA's mandate to establish EUCS, there is the need for an EU standard developing organization (SDO) to create a so-called "technical specification" (TS). This specification is basically a formal standard containing the EUCS requirements which were published by ENISA in draft form last December 2020. The technical specification must follow the processes of the target SDO, which in this case is CEN CENELEC⁷, the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization. At the time of writing this report, CEN CENELEC JTC 13 WG2 (Management Systems and Controls Sets) had taken over that responsibility by establishing the project "Multi-layered approach for a set of requirements for information/cyber security controls for Cloud Services (EUCS 1)". Starting November 2021, **MEDINA (represented by partner Bosch) has been designated by ENISA as technical expert for supporting the development of the technical specification in the EUCS 1 project from CEN CENELEC.**

The timeline of the EUCS 1 project is as follows:

- Circulation of 1st working draft: March-2022
- Acceptance of TS draft: September-2022
- Submission to vote on TS: December-2022
- Closure of vote on TS: March-2023
- Revision of TS (pre-standard): 2026

As observed, this activity extends beyond MEDINA's lifetime, nevertheless participation of selected partners is part of the project's sustainability activities to be presented in D7.9 [7]. Although for the time being this activity has been delayed due to organizational issue within CEN CENELEC, it is our expectation that most of the standardization efforts in MEDINA will be devoted to the successful publication of the EUCS TS. More details on MEDINA's standardization roadmap can be found in Section 4.

3.3 Code of practice for information security controls based on ISO/IEC 27002 for cloud services (ISO/IEC 27017)

As stated in its public abstract⁸ "ISO/IEC 27017:2015 gives guidelines for information security controls applicable to the provision and use of cloud services by providing:

- additional implementation guidance for relevant controls specified in ISO/IEC 27002;
- additional controls with implementation guidance that specifically relate to cloud services."

A notable difference between EUCS and the current version of ISO/IEC 27017, is that the latter does not contain any reference to the topic of continuous (automated) monitoring as required by the MEDINA framework. However, a new project proposal for revising ISO/IEC 27017 was created in April 2021 and approved as "design specification" early 2022, where it is mentioned⁹ "consider other documents relevant to information security controls applicable to cloud services, to determine which control topics and issues that might need to be considered in ISO/IEC 27017, e.g. **German C5, EUCS and SECNUM**. During the revision experts are invited to submit contributions from these and other sources."

⁷ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/>

⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/43757.html>

⁹ Please notice that the cited document is internal to ISO/IEC, therefore it cannot be referenced/attached as appendix to this public deliverable.

A corresponding call for expert contributions was issued by ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27/WG 1 on March 2022 to start shaping the revised ISO/IEC 27017 standard. MEDINA, represented by Bosch in the respective ISO/IEC committee, is already aligning with ENISA to **shape the contributions on topics like continuous (automated) monitoring in order to propose an EUCS-like approach**. If successful, the addition of these novel concepts/requirements in ISO/IEC 27017 has the potential to increase the impact of the MEDINA framework beyond its EU-scope.

Although the revision of ISO/IEC 27017 is planned to finalize late in 2023. MEDINA's contributions (and planned sustainability actions) will be reported in D7.9 [7].

3.4 Open Security Controls Assessment Language (NIST OSCAL)

A topic identified by MEDINA's scouting approach (cf. Section 2) relates to leveraging standardized machine-readable languages in order to fully realize the potential of the framework under development. Such a language would have the potential to create interoperability between different technology providers/CSP, and at the same time conveying relevant information of the continuous certification process as envisioned by the MEDINA architecture (cf. D5.2 [8]). To the best of our knowledge, NIST OSCAL¹⁰ is nowadays the most mature candidate (from a standardization perspective) in this specific field¹¹ just as evidenced by its leverage in relevant certification initiatives like FedRAMP¹².

Almost since the beginning of MEDINA, the consortium has been actively involved in the development of NIST OSCAL. This experience has been also integrated in the ENISA EUCS Experimentation (cf., Section 3.1.3), just as seen in the report documented in Appendix C. At the time of writing, **MEDINA is supporting the discussions between NIST and ENISA in order to further experiment with OSCAL**. This activity is also supported by the proofs of concept developed in the technical WPs of the MEDINA project, which started with the representation of EUCS in OSCAL format just as summarized in the following table.

Table 2. Contribution to NIST OSCAL related to EUCS

OSCAL	EUCS	Examples
Groups/ID	Domain	A7
Groups/title	Category	A7 Operational Security
Groups/parts/prose(objective)	Objective	Ensure proper and regular operation, including appropriate measures for planning and monitoring capacity, protection against malware, logging and monitoring events, and dealing with vulnerabilities, malfunctions and failures.
Groups/Controls/properties/value(label)	Control ID	OPS-02

¹⁰ Please refer to <https://pages.nist.gov/OSCAL/>

¹¹ It is also worth to notice that a founding member of NIST OSCAL (Dr. Michaela Iorga) is part of MEDINA's Expert Stakeholder Group.

¹² <https://www.fedramp.gov/blog/2021-07-20-FedRAMP-Releases-Updated-OSCAL-Templates-Tools/>

OSCAL	EUCS	Examples
Groups/Controls/title	Control	CAPACITY MANAGEMENT - MONITORING
Groups/Controls/parts/prose/ (control-objective)	Control Objective	The capacities of critical resources such as personnel and IT resources are monitored.
Groups/Controls/parts/parts/ properties/value(label)	Requirement ID	OPS-02.3
Groups/Controls/parts/parts/ prose(item)	Requirement	The provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services shall be automatically monitored to guarantee fulfilment of OPS-02.1.

The resulting OSCAL representation of the EUCS requirements will be made available on the MEDINA code repositories during the execution of the project. The consortium has been also using this standardization activity to participate in NIST-organized workshops with the goal of disseminating MEDINA's activities to US-based audiences (see D7.4 [9]).

3.5 The Gaia-X Initiative

Several members of the MEDINA consortium (i.e., Bosch, Fabasoft, FhG, HPE, TECNALIA and XLAB), are members of the so-called Gaia-X Association for Data and Cloud AISBL¹³. This association was founded with the goal of developing and operating the technical framework for the Gaia-X Federation services.

In the timeframe of March 2020 to December 2021, Gaia-X had a dedicated group on Compliance, where MEDINA partners Bosch, Fabasoft, FhG and TECNALIA were very active. The WG Compliance met on a weekly basis to discuss the certification schemes that should be relevant for Gaia-X, as well as to discuss the different assurance levels that could be considered in Gaia-X for the labelling framework.

In addition, the German-funded Gaia-X Federation Services project was set up, to design and implement an orchestration layer between the distributed, federated Clouds that comprise Gaia-X. The core functionalities of these Federation Services include integration, identity and authentication, security as well as compliance. Members of the consortium actively contributed to the design specification of the Continuous Automated Monitoring (CAM)¹⁴ component. In this way, the research of MEDINA methodologies and techniques, such as the metric/evidence-based approach, were actively contributed to a de-facto industry standard. In turn to align with Gaia-X, the definition of the metric template used in the specification has been fully adopted by MEDINA.

Furthermore, Fraunhofer AISEC is currently involved in the implementation of said specification in an open-source project¹⁵ currently coordinated by the eco – Verband der Internetwirtschaft. Since the aim of the implementation task is to re-use existing open-source implementations of this field as much as possible, parts of the open-source components of MEDINA, such as the

¹³ <https://www.gaia-x.eu/who-we-are/association>

¹⁴ <https://www.gxfs.eu/download/1731/>

¹⁵ <https://gitlab.com/gaia-x/data-infrastructure-federation-services/cam>

Clouditor component, are currently being integrated into the implementation of the CAM component, ensuring further reach of the MEDINA activities. Additionally, the MEDINA partner XLAB has been contracted for the implementation of the portal services of the Gaia-X federation services.

Gaia-X is not only significant for MEDINA from a standardization perspective, but it is a central concept for the joint exploitation strategy as discussed in D7.6 [1].

3.6 Security Metrics and Cloud Controls Matrix (Cloud Security Alliance)

While MEDINA has a strong focus on the European approach using the EUCS, it aims to be as compatible to other international standards as possible (cf. Section 3.4). In particular, activities from the Cloud Security Alliance¹⁶ have a strong international relevance for CSPs and thus are also of importance for MEDINA. Dedicated persons from the MEDINA project, such as Christian Banse of Fraunhofer AISEC are part of different working groups within the Cloud Security Alliance, namely the Cloud Controls Matrix v4 (CCMv4) working group as well as a newly established working group on Continuous Audit Metrics. An initial report¹⁷ related to the latter working group has been actively supported by MEDINA, and the developed metrics are being analysed by the corresponding technical WP.

¹⁶ <https://cloudsecurityalliance.org/>

¹⁷ <https://cloudsecurityalliance.org/artifacts/the-continuous-audit-metrics-catalog/>

4 Standardization Roadmap (First Iteration)

This section elaborates on the first version of MEDINA’s standardization roadmap, which is our “guiding light” both for (i) the standardization activities taking place within the project, and also for (ii) our expert opinion on the core topics where SDO/SSO engagement is needed for sustaining MEDINA’s framework and EUCS.

The section starts with a description of the proposed approach for creating the standardization roadmap, followed by a presentation of the identified topics, and their synergies within the SDO/SSO community.

4.1 Methodological Approach

In order to develop MEDINA’s standardization roadmap, the consortium has followed a methodological approach consisting of the activities listed below:

1. The starting point for the roadmap are the project’s scouting activities presented in Section 2.2, which provide the consortium with a landscape overview of SDO/SSO activities associated with the MEDINA framework.
2. The information provided by our scouting activities is then complemented by our interactions with the expert SDO/SSO community. We refer in particular to our ESG¹⁸ members where the following key representatives have been engaged:
 - a. Dr. Eric Vetillard (ENISA¹⁹, EUCS lead).
 - b. Dr. Michaela Iorga (NIST²⁰, OSCAL lead).
 - c. Mrs. Meghan Herster (Oracle, ISO/IEC 27017 lead).
 - d. Dr. Clemens Doubrava/Dr. Patrick Grete (BSI²¹, C5 lead)
3. Finally, for MEDINA is also essential the results coming from our empirical validation of the developed framework (cf. Work Package 6), where input from practitioners is then used to refine both scouting and ESG feedback.

Needless to say, that the presented approach is not a one-time-activity, but an iterative task which refines the roadmap during the execution of the project. Finally, it is also worth mentioning that the standardization roadmap plays an essential role in the project’s sustainability which is expected to last even after MEDINA has finalized.

Next, we present our initial set of standardization topics, as identified for our roadmap based on the approach described in the previous paragraphs.

4.2 Topics for Standardization

Departing from the approach described above, the consortium identified a set of standardization topics which have the potential to increase the impact of MEDINA’s outcomes, while at the same time supporting the uptake of EUCS. These topics are summarized in Table 3. Furthermore, the roadmap was also presented to ENISA in the context of the performed EUCS experimentation (see Section 3.1.3).

¹⁸ Expert Stakeholder Group

¹⁹ European Union Agency for Cybersecurity

²⁰ US National Institute for Standards and Technology

²¹ Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik

Table 3. Topics for Standardization Roadmap

Topic	Description/Comments	MEDINA Contribution/Action Item
<p>Provide <i>implementation</i> guidance about EUCS requirements where some degree of automated monitoring is needed.</p>	<p>Close examination of the “Continuous (Automated) Monitoring” definition in the core EUCS document opens questions related to aspects like frequency for gathering compliance data, reference to use for comparing gathered data, and so forth.</p> <p>More detailed/concrete implementation guidance is needed for CSPs aiming to achieve continuous monitoring. As needed, we even suggest referencing technologies like Cloud Security Posture Management systems, which can greatly support implementation of continuous monitoring.</p>	<p>MEDINA is creating the so-called TOM Implementation Guidance (see D2.1 [3]), which is part of the framework component “Catalogue of Controls & Security Schemes”.</p> <p>This implementation guidance is well suited for SSO where <i>recommended</i> good practices are in scope. An initial assessment has identified Cloud Security Alliance²² as a potential target for this roadmap’s topic, although further discussion with ENISA is also planned.</p>
<p>Provide <i>audit/assessment</i> guidance related to EUCS requirements needing some degree of automated monitoring.</p>	<p>In analogy to the previous topic, we also suggest developing concrete guidance for auditors working on continuous monitoring. Such guidance should tackle aspects like identification of deviations on the continuous monitoring systems, definition of operational effectiveness in the automated monitoring context, and so forth.</p> <p>Such guidance must also provide information about what CABs are expected to do with data coming from the CSPs’ continuous monitoring systems. For example, to guide</p>	<p>The project is contributing with a thoughtful analysis of evidence management for continuous/automated monitoring. Associated tools and techniques will be also part of the MEDINA framework.</p> <p>Developed good practices (as documented in D3.1 [4], D3.2 [10], D3.3 [11], D3.4 [6], D3.5 [12] and D3.6 [13]), for automated management of technical and organizational measures, will be contributed to SSOs like Cloud Security Alliance²² and even ISACA²³. In both cases, the topic of automated audit has taken great importance during the last few years.</p>

²² Online <https://cloudsecurityalliance.org/>

²³ Online <https://www.isaca.org/>

Topic	Description/Comments	MEDINA Contribution/Action Item
	CABs (and CSPs) on actions to take with “compliance fluctuations” identified during the audit period.	
<p>Provide a catalogue of metrics as part of the implementation guidance for EUCS.</p>	<p>The MEDINA team sees the need for a catalogue of metrics to be released as part of the implementation guidance related to continuous monitoring. Such catalogue will reduce the subjectivity of both CSPs and CABs while implementing/assessing a requirement related to continuous monitoring.</p> <p>For our team, the proposed Metrics Catalogue is seen as a necessary requirement for guiding CABs in assessing operational effectiveness and understanding the definition of target values defined by CSPs.</p> <p>The lack of such catalogue might result in partial implementations/assessments of “complex” EUCS requirements.</p>	<p>This very important topic is being directly tackled by MEDINA as presented in D2.1 [3]. The elicited set of metrics might not be in the scope of an SDO for taking over, mainly because of its non-prescriptive nature, so an SSO seems to be also the target audience for this outcome. Besides the discussions with Cloud Security Alliance, it is our belief that ENISA could also profit from publishing such catalogue.</p> <p>Other important aspects of the MEDINA metrics (e.g., the corresponding machine-readable format) are in the focus on the standardization roadmap topic presented below.</p>
<p>Guidance on selecting tools/technologies for automated (continuous) monitoring.</p>	<p>Stakeholders in EUCS, in particular CSPs and CABs, need further guidance on the tools/technologies implied as required for leveraging automated (continuous monitoring). Such tools/technologies can become a security risk by themselves if they cannot provide the required assurance to stakeholders e.g., if a tool has known vulnerabilities.</p>	<p>The proposed guidance is expected to be a result of the validation activities in MEDINA, where the project leverages commercial tools (i.e., the so-called Cloud Security Posture Management²⁴) for integration into the overall framework. While keeping MEDINA’s technology-neutral approach, we aim to discuss with SSOs the developed good practices which can be then profited by early MEDINA/EUCS-adopters.</p>

²⁴ Cloud Security Posture Management (CSPM) refers to those tools used to automatically assess if the configuration of commercial cloud services (mainly IaaS and PaaS) is compliant with specific target values. More information <https://www.techtarget.com/searchsecurity/definition/Cloud-Security-Posture-Management-CSPM>

Topic	Description/Comments	MEDINA Contribution/Action Item
	<p>Furthermore, it is necessary to discuss if the tool/technology itself must be also EUCS certified (if cloud-based) or should provide any other kind of assurance/certification. This might introduce additional complexities (e.g., compositional certification aspects) to the already challenging EUCS High.</p>	<p>At this stage we have identified both Cloud Security Alliance and ISACA as potential target SSO groups for this topic.</p>
<p>Support development of machine-readable formats.</p>	<p>Despite a machine-readable language is not required by EUCS, this is the basis for rolling out continuous (automated) monitoring. For example, providing the EUCS catalogue in a standardized machine-readable format, will benefit automation and adoption by CSPs.</p> <p>However, the machine-readable format should go beyond the representation of EUCS requirements, so it should also cover other elements like automated assessments. Only then, it might be possible to establish a functional ecosystem for continuous audit-based certification as envisioned by MEDINA.</p>	<p>The project is already collaborating with US NIST on their OSCAL initiative (see Section 3.4), which is by far the most promising alternative for a machine-readable language as envisioned by MEDINA. Furthermore, OSCAL is already showing its potential within SSOs like ISO/IEC SC27 where machine-readable representations of well-known catalogues like ISO/IEC 27001 are already being created.</p>
<p>Support the notion of continuous (automated) assessments.</p>	<p>Of utter importance for MEDINA is the adoption of the continuous/automated notion in standardized cloud security requirements. Such concept needs to be extended in EUCS, while in parallel should be also integrated into other well-known security control frameworks.</p>	<p>MEDINA contributes with the empirical validation of EUCS requirements related to continuous (automated) monitoring, which will be then used as initial experience to extend the coverage in the final catalogue being built by CEN CENELEC (see Section 3.2). This notion will be also brought to ISO/IEC (see Section 3.3).</p>

4.3 Next Steps

As seen in the previous section, all the topics in MEDINA’s standardization roadmap are already underway in the project’s technical WPs. Also, Section 3 already presented the SDO/SSO activities of MEDINA which directly relate to the proposed roadmap. At the time of writing this deliverable, the MEDINA team agrees on the following prioritization of standardization efforts derived from the roadmap:

Table 4. MEDINA Roadmap - Next Steps

Roadmap Topic	Prioritization	Rationale
Provide a catalogue of metrics as part of the implementation guidance for EUCS.	High	The notion of Metric is essential for triggering the different functionalities in the MEDINA framework, therefore its criticality from a project’s perspective. We foresee most of our standardization activities going in the direction of contributing the developed catalogue (cf. D2.1 [3]) to relevant SSOs based on the presented strategy (cf. Section 2).
Support the notion of continuous (automated) assessments.	High	EUCS is the basis for MEDINA, not only due to the expected impact it will have in the EU CSP market, but also because it introduces the notion of continuous (automated) monitoring. In that sense, the project will continue its contributions both to ENISA (cf. Section 3.1) and the technical specification being developed by CEN CENELEC (cf. Section 3.2).
Provide <i>implementation</i> guidance about EUCS requirements where some degree of automated monitoring is needed.	Medium	Guidance related to implementation of EUCS requirements is important for the uptake of this new certification scheme, although not critical for the adoption of MEDINA (at least not as the actual EUCS requirements are). Although the corresponding guidance will continue to be developed during the rest of the project’s lifetime, its contribution to relevant SSO will be further discussed with ENISA.
Provide <i>audit/assessment</i> guidance related to EUCS requirements needing some degree of automated monitoring.	Medium	In analogy to the previous topic, the guidance related to audit/assessment for EUCS is also being developed by the project with the goal of contributing it to an SSO after discussing it with ENISA before the project’s finalization.
Support development of machine-readable formats.	Medium	This topic is a consequence of the work being produced by the technical WPs in MEDINA, and despite it might greatly facilitate the adoption of the contributed framework, our belief is that it should not be a showstopper in the mid-term. Therefore, the proposal to continuously scout the

Roadmap Topic	Prioritization	Rationale
		relevant standardization landscape while continuing contributions to NIST (cf. Section 3.4).
Guidance on selecting tools/technologies for automated (continuous) monitoring.	Low	This guidance is important for early EUCS adopters, although our belief is that its development should be a consequence of MEDINA’s exploitation activities (identification of potential market competitors).

5 Conclusions

This deliverable has reported on MEDINA's standardization activities which have taken place during the first half of the project's lifetime. The performed activities included a presentation of the designed approach towards identifying/contributing to relevant SDO/SSO, and a report on the actual activities performed by MEDINA on this specific topic. Our approach is allowing the project to create an impact on activities which are considered as critical for the uptake of our framework e.g., EUCS and CEN CENELEC.

Furthermore, this deliverable also presented the first version of MEDINA's standardization roadmap, which allows the consortium to structure and plan our activities taking place during the second half of the project's lifetime. The topics in the standardization roadmap have been prioritized to maximize the impact of the foreseen framework, while optimizing the usage of standardization resources.

The next (and final) version of this deliverable (D7.9 [7]) will report the latest version of the presented roadmap, including an update on the performed SDO/SSO activities, and the devised standardization activities which are considered essential for the project's sustainability.

6 References

- [1] MEDINA Consortium, “D7.6 Exploitation and sustainability Report-v1,” 2022.
- [2] MEDINA Consortium, “D7.7 Exploitation and sustainability Report-v2,” 2023.
- [3] MEDINA Consortium, “D2.1 Continuously certifiable technical and organizational measures and catalogue of cloud security metrics-v1,” 2021.
- [4] MEDINA Consortium, “D3.1 Tools and techniques for the management of trustworthy evidence-v1,” 2021.
- [5] MEDINA Consortium, “D2.6 Risk-based techniques and tools for Cloud Security Certification-v1,” 2022.
- [6] MEDINA Consortium, “D3.4 Tools and techniques for collecting evidence of technical and organisational measures-v1,” 2021.
- [7] MEDINA Consortium, “D7.9 Standardization Roadmap-v2,” 2023.
- [8] MEDINA Consortium, "D5.2 MEDINA Requirements, Detailed architecture, DevOps infrastructure and CI/CD and verification strategy-v2," 2022.
- [9] MEDINA Consortium, “D7.4 Dissemination and Communication Report-v1,” 2022.
- [10] MEDINA Consortium, “D3.2 Tools and techniques for the management of trustworthy evidence-v2,” 2022.
- [11] MEDINA Consortium, “D3.3 Tools and techniques for the management of trustworthy evidence-v3,” 2023.
- [12] MEDINA Consortium, “D3.5 Tools and techniques for collecting evidence of technical and organisational measures-v2,” 2022.
- [13] MEDINA Consortium, “D3.6 Tools and techniques for collecting evidence of technical and organisational measures-v3,” 2023.

APPENDIX A: Assurance Levels in EUCS (Draft November 2020)

Level	Basic	Substantial	High
Intention	Provide limited assurance through a review by an independent third party that the cloud service is built and operated with procedures and mechanisms to meet the corresponding security requirements at a level intended to minimize the known basic risks of incidents and cyberattacks.	Provide reasonable assurance through evaluation by an independent third party that the cloud service is built and operated with procedures and mechanisms to minimise known cybersecurity risks, and the risk of incidents and cyberattacks carried out by actors with limited skills and resources. The CSP has assessed those risks and implemented suitable controls that, if operating effectively, minimize those risks and meet the corresponding security requirements throughout a specified period.	Provide reasonable assurance through evaluation by an independent auditor that the cloud service is built and operated with procedures and mechanisms to minimise the risk of state-of-the-art cyberattacks carried out by actors with significant skills and resources. The CSP has assessed those risks and implemented suitable controls that operated effectively to minimize those risks and meet the corresponding security requirements throughout a specified period. Security controls are monitored for continuous operation in accordance with their design; they are reviewed, and pen tested to validate their actual ability to prevent or detect security breaches.
Intention rationale	Scope, depth and rigour of the evaluation level is limited to procedures and mechanisms for those security requirements that shall minimize basis risks only.	Scope, depth and rigour of this evaluation level requires the cloud service provider to apply a risk-based approach for the suitable design and implementation of controls that meet the corresponding security requirements. The systematic risk assessment approach and the operating effectiveness (consistent application) of controls throughout a specified period is evaluated by an independent auditor,	Scope, depth and rigour of this evaluation level extends the previous level by additional procedures to be performed for automated controls. Automated monitoring is applied by the CSP to identify exceptions in the application of controls (e.g. changes to the configuration) and initiate corrective actions. Reviews and pen tests are performed by the independent auditor or a third party engaged by the CSP with the objective to identify vulnerabilities that allow to circumvent, override or breach controls.

Level	Basic	Substantial	High
		including for the initial conformity assessment.	
Suitability	This level is suitable for cloud services that are designed to meet typical security requirements on services for non-critical data and systems.	This level is suitable for cloud services that are designed to meet typical security requirements on services for business-critical data and systems.	This level is suitable for cloud services that are designed to meet specific (exceeding assurance level 'substantial') security requirements for mission critical data and systems.
Suitability rationale	This level provides limited assurance that baseline procedures and mechanisms are in place to address security risks and threats in potentially low impact information systems (e.g.: Web site hosting public information). It is typically not suited for Platform or Infrastructure capabilities, used by a large number of services. built on top and that require an elevated level of security. This level demonstrates a willingness to address security, including the application of security guidance from subservice providers.	This level provides reasonable assurance that a set of more stringent security controls is designed and operated to address security risks and threats in potentially moderate impact information systems to protect business critical information (e.g.: Confidential business data, email, CRM – customer relation management systems, personal information). It is suitable for all capabilities types. This level demonstrates a robust and mature holistic security management to provide secure services.	This level provides reasonable assurance that a set of even more stringent security controls is designed and operated to address security risks and threats in potentially high impact information systems to protect mission critical information (e.g. highly confidential business data, patents). The costly and rigorous evaluation process reflects the intention to minimize the risks in using the cloud service.
Attacker profile	Single person with limited skills repeating a known attack with limited resources, not including the ability to perform social engineering attacks.	Small team of persons with hacking abilities and access to a wide range of known hacking techniques, including social engineering, but with limited resources, in particular to launch wide attacks or to discover	Team of highly skilled persons with access to significant resources to design and perform attacks, get insider attacks, discover or buy access to previously unknown vulnerabilities.

Level	Basic	Substantial	High
Attacker rationale	<p>profile</p> <p>Today, this is about removing low-lying fruits and ensuring that cloud services, including simple ones, are designed with security in mind. The objective is to remove the possibility to fall victim to trivial attacks.</p> <p>When such certification becomes mainstream, the requirements should be revised upwards.</p>	<p>previously unknown vulnerabilities.</p> <p>This is the “standard” attacker, corresponding to most real-life attacks used to disclose information, steal resources, deny service, or tamper with a service.</p> <p>Their main characteristics come from the definition of the level: “known attacks” and “limited resources”. Note that this definition is quite ambitious and allows the use of attacks that leverage several vulnerabilities.</p>	<p>This is the sophisticated attacker, against which detection and mitigation is more efficient than resistance. At this level, it may be difficult to define precisely a way to analyse that the objective has been met, in particular because there is an expectation to minimize risks through various mitigation methods.</p>
Scope	<p>As defined by the service description and the controls pertaining to this level, including processes and the software (understood as result of a development process) underlying the service.</p>	<p>As defined by the service description and the controls pertaining to this level, including processes and the software (understood as result of a development process) underlying the service.</p> <p>Operating effectiveness of the controls shall be demonstrated.</p>	<p>As defined by the service description and the controls pertaining to this level, including processes and the software (understood as result of a development process) underlying the service.</p> <p>Operating effectiveness of the controls shall be demonstrated. (including automated monitoring if required by the control definition).</p>
Scope rationale	<p>This may need to be rephrased, depending on the relationship between “controls” and “requirements”.</p> <p>Here, the idea would be to include all controls in their general form, but without the more detailed requirements</p>	<p>We refer to the same controls from the Basic assurance level, but with the stronger refinements or enhancements (e.g., (mandated techniques, thresholds, etc.).</p>	<p>We refer to the same controls from the Substantial assurance level, but with the higher refinements or enhancements.</p> <p>Enhancements often included additional constraints, references to state-of-the-art requirements, and automated monitoring of some controls.</p>

Level	Basic	Substantial	High
	that may be added for higher levels.	Requirements must include a limited pen testing using known attacks.	
Depth	<p>Inspection solely, based on a check for completeness and coherence of the provided documentation on processes and design intended to confirm the fulfilment of technical and organizational measures, and interactions between the auditor and the CSP at the beginning and at the conclusion of the inspection.</p> <p>A report following defined procedures is generated by the inspection body.</p> <p>Once a year, a documentation update is provided for third-party review of the continued development and operation of the service.</p>	<p>Additional to the requirements of the Basic level: On-site audit including interviews and inspecting samples, plus a verification that the implementation follows the specified policies and procedures, and an additional focus on development activities, for instance on the functional tests performed.</p> <p>On the initial assessment and once a year, the operating effectiveness of the security controls, <i>i.e.</i> their operation as designed, needs to be demonstrated over the previous period.</p>	<p>Additional to the requirements of the Substantial level, specific requirements on the monitoring and testing of the controls, <i>i.e.</i> their operation as intended to protect from attacks or detect them, needs to be demonstrated.</p> <p>Different measures may be used, such as technical reviews, and penetration testing shall be performed by qualified personnel, following a multi-year plan that needs to be validated in the audit.</p>
Depth rationale	<p>The inspection focuses on completeness, coherence and plausibility of the documentation. It needs to be an efficient process that mostly focuses on the existence of processes, and of a secure by design approach, to demonstrate the proper design and existence</p>	<p>The full audit aims at providing reasonable assurance that the security controls are properly designed and operate effectively, <i>i.e.</i> as designed, over a period of time.</p>	<p>The audit aims at providing the same reasonable assurance as for the Substantial level.</p> <p>The main addition in depth come from additional requirements for level Substantial such as automated monitoring and penetration testing, which are intended to demonstrate that the controls remain effective under strenuous conditions.</p>

Level	Basic	Substantial	High
	of security measures to protect the cloud service.		
Rigour	<p>The assessment is performed by the CSP and driven by a standardised checklist.</p> <p>An accredited third-party then audits the assessment report and its supporting documentation.</p>	<p>The assessment is performed by an accredited third-party, and it is driven by a risk analysis performed by the CSP, which is in the audit scope.</p>	<p>The assessment is performed as for the Substantial level, but the CAB needs to be authorized by the NCCA to it has the required competencies to audit the specific requirements of the Substantial level.</p> <p>More rigour is expected in the definition and application of policies, usually as defined in requirements specific to the controls (e.g. the need to demonstrate the coverage of functional tests used in development).</p> <p>A specifically accredited and authorized CAB needs to be involved in the performance of vulnerability identification and penetration testing activities.</p>
Rigour rationale	<p>The assessment follows all items in a checklist suited to the targeted cloud service, and its results are reviewed by an accredited third-party.</p>	<p>A full audit is performed by an independent third-party, and the checklist approach is replaced by a more rigorous risk-based approach, allowing the auditor to identify controls that require specific attention.</p>	<p>The rigour remains mostly the same as for level Substantial as it corresponds to typical audit conditions.</p> <p>Nevertheless, specific requirements explicitly increase the level of rigour on some controls by requiring additional deliverables from the CSP.</p> <p>The addition of testing by a CAB provides an additional level of rigour around the critical activities of vulnerability identification and penetration testing</p>

APPENDIX B: Basic EUCS Questionnaire Contribution (excerpt)

ReqID	Requirement	Level	Question ID	Statement/Questions	Answer	Evidence
OPS-01.1	The CSP shall document and implement procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources), which shall include forecasting future capacity requirements in order to identify usage trends and manage system overload	Basic	Q1-OPS-01.1	Does the CSP document procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources)?		- Capacity plan - Specific capacity procedures
			Q2-OPS-01.1	Do procedures include forecasting future capacity requirements in order to identify usage trends and manage system overload?		- Capacity plan (encompasses future capacity requirements) - Specific capacity procedures
			Q3-OPS-01.1	Does the CSP implement procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources)?		- Capacity plan audit
OPS-01.2	The CSP shall meet the requirements included in contractual agreements with cloud customers regarding the provision of the cloud service in case of capacity bottlenecks or personnel and IT resources outages	Basic	Q1-OPS-01.2	Does the CSP meet the requirements included in contractual agreements with cloud customers regarding the provision of the cloud service in case of capacity bottlenecks?		- Monitoring reports - Non-conformities to the contract (if there are non-compliances)
			Q2-OPS-01.2	Does the CSP meet the requirements included in contractual agreements with cloud customers regarding the provision of the cloud service in case of IT resources outages?		- Monitoring reports - Non-conformities to the contract/SLA (if there are non-compliances)
OPS-01.3	The capacity projections shall be considered in accordance with the service level agreement for planning and preparing the provisioning	High				
OPS-02.1	The CSP shall define and implement technical and organizational safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement	Basic	Q1-OPS-02.1	Does the CSP define technical safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?		- Multidimensional QoS prediction methods

			Q2-OPS-02.1	Does the CSP implement technical safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	- Service level agreement - SLA compliance report
			Q3-OPS-02.1	Does the CSP define organizational safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	- Multi-dimensional QoS measures
			Q4-OPS-02.1	Does the CSP implement organizational safeguards for the monitoring of provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services to ensure compliance with the service level agreement?	- Service level agreement - SLA compliance report
OPS-02.2	The CSP shall make available to the cloud customer the relevant information regarding capacity and availability on a self-service portal	High			
OPS-02.3	The provisioning and de-provisioning of cloud services shall be automatically monitored to guarantee fulfilment of OPS-02.1	High			
OPS-03.1	The CSP shall enable CSCs to control and monitor the allocation of the system resources assigned to them, if the corresponding cloud capabilities are exposed to the CSCs	Basic	Q1-OPS-03.1	Does the CSP enable CSCs to control and monitor the allocation of the system resources assigned to them, if the corresponding cloud capabilities are exposed to the CSCs?	- Contract - SLA - Privileges to use the monitoring and control tools

APPENDIX C: Report to ENISA on EUCS Experimentation

This report discusses lessons learned related to the experimentation performed by the MEDINA team on the topic of continuous (automated) monitoring, just as required by the High Assurance baseline of the draft version of the European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Service (EUCS). Besides the reported process and obtained results, we also provide a set of recommendations to relevant stakeholders (in particular Cloud Service Providers and Auditors) with the goal of supporting the uptake of EUCS for High Assurance.